

INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES OF GLASS FIBRE/NANOPARTICULATE REINFORCED POLYESTER RESIN

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SUMMARY

The SFPO test and the SFFT have been utilised to determine the interfacial properties of a glass fibre and two resin materials; i) polyester resin (PR) ii) ormosil nanomodified polyester resin (NR). Both methods led to similar trends in the test data. Failure mechanisms were studied using a range of techniques.

Keywords: Interface, Nanocomposite, SFPO, SFFT, ToF-SIMS, AFM

INTRODUCTION

Advanced fibre reinforced composites (FRCs) often use cross-linked epoxy and polyester resins as matrix materials. A limiting factor in their use is the relatively low toughness of the matrix material which can lead to a tendency for cracking. Over the past 30 years there has been a great deal of interest in improving the mechanical properties, notably the toughness, of polymeric matrices by the addition of various micrometre-sized modifying phases to the resin system such as phenolic beads [1], carbon beads [1], and rubber particles [2,3].

More recently, attention has been given to replacing micrometer-sized reinforcements with nanometre-sized modifying phases. Nanomaterials potentially offer higher improvements because they have significantly higher specific surface areas compared to their micro-phase counterparts; this can lead to the requirement for lower modifying phase loadings, which gives rise to reduced disruption of the primary reinforcement. There is also the possibility of novel fracture mechanisms on the nanoscale.

The interphase is a critical region in any composite material. The success or failure of the composite can depend upon the nature of the interphase as load is transferred across one phase to another – such load transfer occurs for instance across the interface of an adhesive joint and between the precipitates and the matrix in metal alloys, as well as at a fibre/matrix interface in FRCs. Understanding the behaviour of such interphases and their influence on mechanical properties is very important. Time-of-flight secondary ion mass spectrometry (ToF-SIMS) has been used previously as a fractographic tool to study interphases and to help provide information about fracture mechanisms and determine locus of failure in FRCs [4-6].

The toughening effect of nanoparticle additions to a baseline polyester system have been investigated previously [7]. In this paper we describe the use of the single fibre pull-out (SFPO) test and the single fibre fragmentation test (SFFT) to characterize the interfacial properties of a glass fibre in; i) a baseline polyester (PR), ii) a nanomodified polyester resin (NR). While each of these micromechanical tests has been used extensively to characterise interfacial properties independently, there appear to have been few attempts to apply both test methods to the same materials in tandem.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Two materials have been investigated; i), a baseline resin system (PR), and ii) the baseline material modified with the addition of organically modified silicas (ormosil) nanoparticles (NR). The PR system was an unsaturated polyester resin, supplied without the addition of the silica thixotropic agent, (Crystic 2-406 PA, Scott Bader, Wellingborough, UK). Phenyl modified ormosil nanoparticles, produced via a modified Stöber hydrolytic route, were manufactured and supplied by Hay *et al* (University of Surrey) – see reference [8]. The nanoparticles have a diameter in the order of 150 nm. These were incorporated into the PR system to manufacture a 1 vol.% nanomodified material, NR, using a processing route described elsewhere [9]. Both resins were mixed and cured according to the specification of the manufacturer using 0.5 vol.% of initiator, Catalyst M (methyl ethyl ketone peroxide). All samples received a 24 hour room temperature cure followed by a 3 hour 80°C post cure.

The fibres used in the investigation were commercially available 600 tex silane based sized E-glass with a nominal fibre diameter of 12 μm (Hybron 2001/600TEX, PPG, USA). The fibre sizing is compatible with both unsaturated polyester and epoxy resin systems.

Single Fibre Pull-out (SFPO) Test

Specialist SFPO sample preparation and testing apparatus were used to conduct SFPO investigations, the development of which are described in detail elsewhere [10]. An advanced SFPO data reduction methodology has been used which enables an apparent IFSS, τ_{app} , a stress for debonding τ_d , a frictional stress τ_f , and a critical interfacial energy release rate G_{ic} , to be determined, see Zhandarov and Mäder [11] for details.

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)

The surface morphology and roughness of pulled-out fibres post SFPO testing was measured using an atomic force microscope (Digital Instruments D3100, USA). AFM was conducted in the tapping mode on two regions near to the fibre entry point with the matrix, as shown schematically in Figure 1. The area close to the fibre entry point will have experienced less friction damage upon extraction and hence have a more preserved fracture surface for analysis. Images of the sample surface were performed across a 2 μm x 2 μm area. The instrument cantilever had a 10 nm silicon nitride tip and was operated at a scan rate of 1.48 Hz with a resolution of 512 x 512. The surface roughness of each image was measured and an adhesion force measured.

Figure 1 – Schematic of the location of AFM scan areas on pulled-out fibres

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM was conducted using a cold field emission scanning electron microscope (Hitachi S-4000, Japan) interfaced with image software (Quartz PCI). In order to reduce electrostatic charging of the sample, a 5 nm sputter of fine grained gold was deposited onto the samples using a sputter coater (Emitech K575X Turbo Sputter Coater, UK). On samples where ToF-SIMS was performed, SEM was always conducted post ToF-SIMS analysis due to the necessity to deposit a sputter coating onto the sample surface. An accelerating potential of 20 kV was used for all SEM studies described in this paper.

A specially designed cradle (Figure 2) was used to mount pulled-out fibres which could be transferred between the sample sledge of the scanning electron microscope and the sample platen of the ToF-SIMS instrument, so avoiding handling of the sample and possible damage. Another feature of the cradle was that the extracted fibre end was supported. A standard circular 10 mm aluminium sample stub was cut in half to provide a semicircular stub, which could be raised or lowered so that the fibre rested on it. Supporting the sample made it more stable for SEM, providing better micrographs, and in addition improved the secondary ion yield during ToF-SIMS analysis by reducing secondary ion shadowing effects as described by Lee [12].

Figure 2 – SFPO specimen mounting cradle

Time-of-Flight Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (ToF-SIMS)

ToF-SIMS analysis was performed using a TOF.SIMS 5 (ION-TOF GmbH, Münster, Germany), fitted with a bismuth liquid metal ion source. Polyatomic Bi_3^+ was used as the primary ion source using an accelerating voltage of 25 keV and a primary ion current of 0.3 pA. The bunched mode was selected to obtain spectra with high mass resolution, $M/\Delta M > 10000$, and a spot size of about 4 μm diameter. Spectra were recorded for 60 seconds over an area of 200 x 200 μm^2 at a resolution of 128 x 128 pixels ensuring that the ion dose remained well below the static limit of 10^{12} ions/ cm^2 /analysis.

Single Fibre Fragmentation Test (SFFT)

In order to perform the SFFT a strain to failure ratio of 3:1 must exist between matrix and fibre. To fulfil this requirement 20 phr of tricresyl phosphate (TCP) plasticiser was added to the PR and NR resin systems. SFFT samples were prepared using a method described elsewhere [13]. Testing was performed using specialist apparatus – see reference [14] for details. Samples were strained at a displacement rate of 0.13 mm/min. The fragmentation test was interrupted at 1% strain intervals between 3% and 12% applied strain. The fragment lengths, debond lengths and number of matrix cracks were recorded at each strain increment using the apparatus.

The standard Kelly-Tyson data reduction method was used as well as the cumulative stress transfer function (CSTF) data reduction methodology. The latter method considers debonding and plasticity effects providing a more sophisticated method of analysing SFFT data than the classic Kelly-Tyson model, as described in [14]. To perform the Kelly-Tyson analysis it was

necessary to conduct single filament tests, the data from which are presented in Table 1. The average fragment length, \bar{l} , was measured from the SFFT data. The methods to determine the critical length, l_c , and σ_{fu} are described elsewhere [13].

Table 1 – E-glass fibre properties (10 mm gauge length)

Average σ (GPa)	1.4 \pm 0.4
Average fibre diameter (μm)	12.3 \pm 1.0
Weibull Modulus	3.3

The CSTF is a more sophisticated SFFT data reduction methodology, which considers debonding and plasticity effects and incorporates the matrix tensile properties. In order to perform CSTF analysis additional material property data is required as presented in Table 2.

Table 2 – Input data SFPO and CSTF, respectively for data reduction. Parameters marked with a * are experimentally determined data)

Fibre Properties		
Longitudinal fibre modulus (GPa)	76.0	
Transverse fibre modulus (GPa)	76.0	
Longitudinal Poisson's ratio of fibre	0.22	
Transverse Poisson's ratio of fibre	0.22	
Shear modulus of fibre (Pa)	31.1	
Longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient of fibre (SI units)	4.90×10^{-6}	
Transverse thermal expansion coefficient of fibre (SI units)	4.90×10^{-6}	
Diameter of fibre* (m)	1.23×10^{-5}	
Friction coefficient	0.2	
Matrix Properties		
Elastic modulus of matrix* (GPa)	PR	NR
Poisson's ratio of matrix	1.34	0.63
Thermal expansion coefficient of matrix (SI units)	0.34	
Tensile yield strength of the matrix* (MPa)	1.00×10^{-4}	
Cold draw strength of the matrix* (MPa)	8.31	3.83
	26.5	15.0
Specimen Properties		
Applied stress i.e. $E_m \times \epsilon_c$ (Pa)	Input value	
Matrix volume fraction	0.999375	
Stress free temperature	0	

The shear stress profile for each fragment is converted into a fibre-matrix stress profile, which is averaged in the following equation:

$$CSTF = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} \int_0^{L_i} \sigma_f(x) dx}{\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} L_i} \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of fragments, L_i , is the fragment length for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$, and $\sigma_f(x)$ is the tensile stress at a distance x from the fibre end. These calculations were performed using a computer program, with experimental data and other information inputted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SFPO Data

Typical force-displacement plots produced from SFPO testing of the PR and NR systems are presented in Figure 3. The SFPO plots follow the expected shape. It can be observed that the peak load is higher for the NR sample and there is a difference in area of the extraction region of the force-displacement plot. The processed data are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 – Average (of at least 20 samples) and standard deviation of processed SFPO data for plain resin (PR) and nanomodified resin (NR), AFM average roughness values R_a of fracture surfaces after pull-out and SFFT average (of five samples) and standard deviation for τ_{app} from Kelly-Tyson and CSTF values at 12 % applied strain.

Sample	τ_{app} (MPa) (SFPO)	τ_d (MPa)	τ_f (MPa)	G_{ic} (J/m ²)	R_a (nm)	τ_{app} (MPa) (Kelly-Tyson)	CSTF (MPa m/m)
PR	28.3 ± 5.9	63.3 ± 11.1	6.6 ± 3.0	32.4 ± 10.2	2.3 ± 1.0	17.3 ± 2.6	730 ± 84.0
NR	34.7 ± 7.6	61.4 ± 11.3	9.3 ± 3.1	42.4 ± 14.5	2.9 ± 2.9	10.6 ± 1.8	663 ± 87.2

Figure 3 – Typical SFPO force-displacement plots for PR and NR systems in comparison.

Based on the mechanical data presented in Table 3 it is clear that there are some differences between the interfacial properties of the glass fibre PR system and the glass fibre NR system. There is an increase in τ_{app} of approximately 23% between the PR and NR systems from SFPO testing, suggesting that a stronger interface is formed between the NR and the glass fibre.

There is little difference in the stress value required to initiate debonding between the fibre and the matrix material, τ_d , 63.3 MPa and 61.4 MPa respectively for the PR and NR systems. The τ_d parameter provides information relating to the physio-chemical bonding, or adhesion properties, between the fibre and matrix. The similar values indicate very little difference in the adhesion level between the glass fibre and the two resin systems in the non-destructive region before crack initiation. Therefore the nanoparticle addition to the resin system appears to have little or no effect on the physio-chemical bonding between the matrix and fibre.

The frictional stress in the debonded zone, τ_f , for the NR system, is approximately 42% higher than that of the PR system, 9.3 MPa compared to 6.6 MPa. There is evidently more friction between the fibre and the NR during fibre pull-out.

The G_{ic} is also higher for the NR system than for the PR system, 42.4 J/m² to 32.4 J/m². This increase, of approximately 31% for G_{ic} , is interesting given that it relates to the ability to propagate a crack, yet the adhesion between the fibre and matrix, as measured by the τ_d value is approximately the same for both resin types. It is considered that the nanoparticles near the propagating crack tip could cause a more tortuous pathway for crack progression, hence increasing G_{ic} , a phenomenon considered for toughness increases observed in nanomodified polymer systems, as discussed by Jesson *et al* [7].

AFM and SEM Analysis

AFM was used to measure the average roughness of two regions on the pulled-out fibre. The pulled-out fibre surface extracted from the NR exhibited an average roughness value 26% rougher than the pulled-out fibre surface extracted from the PR system, with associated R_a values of 2.9 nm and 2.3 nm respectively. The AFM image for an unembedded glass fibre reference sample had an average roughness of 1.2 nm. The embedded fibres have a higher roughness than the pristine fibres due to remnants of resin adhering to them. This is expected and a sign of good adhesion between the fibre and matrix. The AFM tapping mode images of Figure 4 reveal these differences between pristine glass fibre (a) and fracture surfaces after pull-out of PR (b) and NR (c).

There is significantly more scatter in the NR roughness values which have a standard deviation of 2.9 compared to a standard deviation of 1.0 for the PR, as the error bars in Figure 5 show. The IFSS and the G_{ic} values of the SFPO tests using the NR matrix are higher than those using the PR matrix as shown also in Figure 5. It is interesting to note that the scatter in the data is much larger for the NR in all of these measurements, suggesting that the nanomodification causes more variation. Based on these analyses it would seem that there is a relationship between an increase in pulled-out fibre surface roughness, IFSS and the energy required to propagate a crack, G_{ic} .

There were no distinguishable differences between the SEM micrographs, not presented here, of the pulled-out fibre surfaces from the different resin types.

Figure 4 – AFM tapping mode images of pristine glass fibre (a) and fracture surfaces after pull-out of PR (b) and NR (c).

Figure 5 – Comparison of IFSS and G_{ic} , with the average roughness, R_a , of the pulled out fibre surface from PR and the NR systems.

ToF-SIMS Analysis

The ToF-SIMS analyses, rather than identifying differences between the pulled-out fibres from the two different resin systems, actually indicated that the fracture surfaces are chemically very similar, as can be seen in the spectral comparison of the two, Figure 6. Peak assignment of silicon containing fragments is confused by silicon presence in both the glass and the nanoparticles, but also from PDMS contamination which made it difficult to determine the influence, if any, of the nanoparticle addition to the NR and the subsequent failure mechanism.

Figure 6 – Positive spectra from mass range 0-200 u of pulled-out fibre surfaces from a) the PR and b) the NR

SFFT: Kelly-Tyson Method

The interfacial properties were examined using the conventional Kelly-Tyson data reduction method. Using the Kelly-Tyson data reduction method, τ_{app} has been calculated and plotted against strain for each resin type, as shown in Figure 7. τ_{app} increases with applied strain as the fragment lengths become smaller, which is based on the assumption that the a better interface leads to shorter fragment lengths. Based on this data reduction technique, the system based on glass fibre embedded within the PR matrix has a higher τ_{app} , 17.3 MPa than the system with the fibre embedded in the NR system, 10.6 MPa at 12% strain. This data conflicts with the SFPO data which showed the NR to have a higher value for τ_{app} , as can be seen in Table 3. From Table 2 it is clear however that the two matrix systems have different tensile properties. The lower yield strength for the NR means less strain is transferred into the fragments during the SFFT which gives misleading τ_{app} values as discussed by Lane *et al* [15]. The CSTF data reduction technique has been applied to provide a more sophisticated method of analysing the SFFT data which attempts to account for differences in resin properties.

Figure 7 – τ_{app} from Kelly-Tyson data reduction

SFFT: Cumulative Stress Transfer Function (CSTF)

The CSTF values were calculated using Equation 1 and plotted against the strain, as presented in Figure 8. Using CSTF data reduction technique aligns the data for both resins types with very little difference between the values at each strain increment. The CSTF level decreases with applied strain in accordance with the assumptions of the data reduction method that a smaller fragment is subject to lower levels of stress. Interfacial debonding further reduces the CSTF value.

It is proposed that the nanoparticles can inhibit the debonding process perhaps in a similar way to that described in the previous section for SFPO failure creating a more tortuous path for the debonding crack. However, less debonding occurs during SFFT compared to SFPO testing, hence the benefit is less pronounced. Furthermore, friction upon extraction of the fibre during SFPO testing gives rise to the increases in interfacial properties as rougher fracture surfaces pass over each other. This mechanism is not apparent during the SFFT and hence the values for CSTF are similar.

Figure 8 – Fragmentation data analysed by Cumulative Stress Transfer Function (CSTF)

CONCLUSIONS

The interfacial properties for PR and NR have been determined using both the SFPO test and SFFT. AFM, SEM and ToF-SIMS have been used to complement the SFPO data. It is proposed that an increase in τ_{app} is observed as a result from increased friction between the fracture surfaces upon extraction of the single fibre as a result of nanoparticles disrupting the crack front causing a more tortuous pathway and hence rougher debond surface. The rougher debond surface was identified from AFM measurements. ToF-SIMS and SEM were unable to distinguish any differences between the fibres post pull-out from the different resin systems.

The Kelly-Tyson data reduction technique of SFFT data was invalid due to differences in the matrix properties therefore the CSTF methodology was applied. The CSTF values are similar for both resin types suggesting equivalent interfacial quality is achieved with both resin systems.

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